

**INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE
LEARNING VILLAGES, CULTURAL
HERITAGE AND RURAL LANDSCAPES**

**Kalamata, Greece
20th of April 2023
BOOK OF ABSTRACTS**

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International Conference
Learning Villages, Cultural Heritage, and
Rural Landscapes

Kalamata, Greece, April 20, 2023

PROGRAMME

Registration (09:00-09:30)

Session 1: Heritage Education and Interpretation (09:30-11:00)

09:30-09:45: *Community Maps. A Tool for Community Cohesion and Heritage Education*

Martín Gómez-Ullate, Alfonso Vázquez Atochero

09:45-10:00: *Three Cultures and Others in Cáceres. A Model for the Study and Transmission of the Soundscape in History*

Pilar Barrios, Francisco Javier Barra Sanz

10:00-10:15: *The Archaeological Site as a Source of Inspiration from the Past to the Present and the Future*

Ioanna Ravani

10:15-10:30: *Cultural Heritage as a Potential Driver for Community Development – The Medieval Tower of Vila Marim in North Portugal as a Case Study*

Teresa Sequeira, Herminia Gonçalves, Veronika Joukes, and António Pirra

10:30-10:45: *Las Candelas de Deleitosa. A Case Study on Heritage Education*

Alba Fernández López, Juana Gómez Pérez

10:45-11:00: Discussion

Coffee Break (11:00-11:30)

Session 2: Interdisciplinary Approaches (11:30-13:15)

11:30-11:45: *A Heritage Park in the Making: The Parrhasian Heritage Park of the Peloponnese*

Nota Pantzou, D.G. Romano, M. Davison, and M. Voyatzis

11:45-12:00: *Sustainable Cultural Management of the Olive Heritage for the Promotion of Culture and Local Economy: The “Routes of the Olive Tree”*

Marinella Katsilieri, George Karabatos

12:00-12:15: *The Archaeological Chart of the Municipality of Sabrosa: An Essential Tool for Managing Municipal Heritage and Territorial Planning in Rural Areas*

Gerardo Vidal Gonçalves, Dina Borges Pereira

12:15-12:30: *The MoCaCu Project: A Portable Unit for the Digitization, Documentation, Characterization and Conservation of Movable Cultural Heritage Artifacts in Remote Areas of Greece*

Afroditi Kamara, Nikolaos Zacharias, Vasiliki Valantou, Eleni Palamara, and Vayia Panayiotidis

12:30-12:45: *Historical Tungsten Mines of Vila Marim, Vila Real (Galicia-North Portugal Euroregion): An Adventure Geotourism Attraction that Supports Sustainable Conservation*

David M. Freire-Lista, Veronika Joukes, and Carla C. Cunha de Sousa

12:45-13:00: *The Project "KALAMATA 1821, Roads of Freedom". An Interdisciplinary Approach towards the Celebrations for the Greek War of Independence*

Nikolaos Zacharias, Vayia Panayiotidis, Vasiliki Valantou, G. Malaperdas, E. Triantafyllidis, G. Rigas

13:00-13:15: Discussion

Lunch Break (13:15-14:00)

Session 3: Digital Applications (14:00-15:30)

14:00-14:15: *DigiSmall: Organizing Small - Local Museums Towards a Digital Era*

Vassilis Pouloupoulos, Afroditi Kamara, Marietta Papakonstantinou, Manolis Wallace, and Manolis Mauromatis

14:15-14:30:

Despoina Lampada, Afroditi Kamara, and Yorgos Tzedopoulos

14:30-14:45: *Learning Villages Must Listen to Stories*

Michael Meimaris

14:45-15:00: *Digital Registration of Cultural Heritage Elements through a Crowdsourcing Web-Based Application*

Filothei Chalvatza, Sokratis Karkalas

15:00-15:15: *Pannonias Medieval Digital Old Lands: Digital Humanities, History and Archaeology for Culture and Tourism*

Gerardo Vidal Gonçalves, Dina Borges Pereira

15:15-15:30: Discussion

Coffee break (15:30-16:00)

Session 4: Sustainability and Biodiversity (16:00-17:45)

16:00-16:15: *Nutritional Self-Sufficiency in Krini Trikalon and the Active Role of the Cultural Association of Krini*

Maria Pritsiouli, Apostolos Lakiaras

16:15-16:30: *Iupiter*

Tiberio Moscardelli

16:30-16:45: *Learning Villages with Value: The Case of the LEARNVIL Approach in Vila Marim, Portugal*

Herminia Gonçalves, Teresa Sequeira António Pirra, and Veronika Joukes

16:45-17:00: *Terra Maronesa, a Collaborative Community that Invests in Networking*

Carla C. Cunha de Sousa, Veronika Joukes

17:00-17:15: *Dialogue and Action for the Future: Developing the Community-Led Revitalisation of a Small Mountain Village through a Multi-Stakeholder Model*

Panagiotis Giannakopoulos

17:15-17:30: *Rural Areas: Smart Tips on the Road to Sustainability*

Konstantinos Asikis

17:30-17:45: Discussion and Closing Remarks

ABSTRACTS

SESSION 1: HERITAGE EDUCATION AND INTERPRETATION

Community Maps. A Tool for Community Cohesion and Heritage Education

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The places in the biographies of the inhabitants of rural villages are intertwined with their memories and are an ideal thread for conducting life stories and creating community maps. Community maps are a tool that shows that maps are much more than a cartographic representation, as they express the idea of place (chronotopes, spatial/temporal configurations), summarize the cosmivision of those who inhabit it and have lived it and felt it, and at the same time, locate the symbols of the territory and the natural confines within which the community recognizes itself.

In fact, the memory of the place always generates a juxtaposition between the practices carried out there in a past, transformed past, and the new generations, the "Other", felt as an alterity, showing the social change in value systems through the comparison of spatio-temporal practices.

Community maps rescue and confront generational use and social practices of relevant spaces of the place, linked to collective action (feast places, workplaces, water places ...) and marked with names, meanings, tales, and experiences. Thus, they are a powerful anthropological tool with impact in many senses.

Heritage Education should make intense use of community maps, since they broaden the standards and classification of cultural heritage, highlighting places, other than solely those officially recognized and regulated.

In this paper, we discuss definition, models, cases and state-of-art of community maps, and we will analyze two case studies in the province of Cáceres, where we conduct ethnographic research: Torreorgaz and Torrequemada.

Three Cultures and Others in Cáceres. A Model for the Study and Transmission of the Soundscape in History

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In the old Town of Cáceres, we find different sites, stories and legends that show us long periods of coexistence and others of controversies and ruptures between cultures and religions; convents, churches built on mosques or synagogues, cisterns, palaces and noble houses, etc. The soundscape is part of the imaginary, showing moments of fraternity with three specifically significant sounds of three cultures: the bells, the shofar and the voice of the muezzin, without forgetting other musical manifestations, which already indicate Christianity, Judaism and Islam. It was precisely on 30 November 2022 that the manual ringing of bells was recognised as an intangible heritage of humanity.

An essential and very present part of this moment in history is to analyse the cultures that have left their mark and ways of coexistence in Cáceres. Through the study of architectural remains and the recreation of musical activities, we dramatise those that may have developed in the social, civic and spiritual life of this city.

In this seminar that we have been developing during this year and that we will continue to work on with our students, future teachers, we are living the simultaneous sound of these three cultures very much in the present. It is precisely now that we are making progress in these three sounds that make up the soundscape, giving life to the stones inside and outside the walls of Cáceres. We are designing a didactic documentary, using representative characters and emblematic buildings (the tower of the wells, the tower of Bujaco, the palace of Moctezuma, the old Synagogue (now the chapel of St. Anthony of the Ravine), the synagogue outside the walls in the Palace of the Island, etc.). All this will lead us to understand the cultural life of these three cultures and others before and after them.

This theme focuses on one of the main research profiles of the MUSAEXI group "Musical heritage, culture and education" of the University of Extremadura analyzing musical heritage. On this occasion we want to highlight heritage education, essentially referring to musical heritage within the history and culture of our Extremaduran Community and the reality that is clearly shown from our land in the meeting of cultures.

The Archaeological Site as a Source of Inspiration from the Past to the Present and the Future

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In this paper we present the results of a completed Erasmus+ project implemented by archaeological and educational organizations in Greece, Italy and Spain who, through the collaboration of different scientific specialties, proposed educational methods and tools for a holistic approach to the archaeological site and its impact to the community. "ArchaeoSchool for the Future: a sustainability approach" (<http://archaeoschool.eu/>) used the existence of archaeological sites from the Greco-Roman era in three closely associated areas of Europe as a basis for developing a strategic approach to strengthen the links between the school and its local environment, deepening concepts of local and European identity, and improving the employment opportunities of young people.

The archaeological site is a broad field of study and research that can be a starting point for an interdisciplinary approach to various issues such as social, natural, environmental, economic, etc. The main purpose was to discover those aspects of the past that can be an inspiration for the improvement of modern society for the present and the future. Its key areas of interest are the integration of career awareness into curricula, strengthening the students' skills and competences in order for them to become active European citizens, and the teachers' professional development. For the study of archaeological sites were proposed innovative educational methods of non-formal learning such as Knowledge Building and Education for Sustainable Development, advanced new technology tools that support the above methods and collaborative creation, as well as and 3D virtual world simulation.

Cultural Heritage as a Potential Driver for Community Development – The Medieval Tower of Vila Marim in North Portugal as a Case Study

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Vila Marim is a parish located in the town of Vila Real, in the north of Portugal. This parish has a typical framework of low-density Portuguese territories: few inhabitants, aged and with a low level of education and a well-preserved natural heritage. In terms of built cultural heritage and despite not being a particularly rich parish, a mysterious medieval tower stands out, the so-called “Torre de Quintela”.

This tower, classified as a national monument, is believed to date from the reign of D. Afonso III (1248-1279), stands sober, strong and dominant over the entire parish, constituting a true identity element.

Several cultural and tourist initiatives have already been developed there in a sporadic and non-professional way, and in quite a few events the local population had an active role. In this communication we will exemplify the activities that took place during the international training week of the Erasmus+ project LEARNVIL (Learning Villages: Citizenship, Entrepreneurship, Heritage & Environmental Education for Rural Sustainable Development) in September 2022.

Within the scope of the LEARNVIL project, a central question arises: How can more structured initiatives be promoted, including the physical recovery of the heritage? Or in other words: With what kind of appealing activity program can one generate income and reinforce the identity feeling of the local community through the Tower?

The upcoming opening of a framework for community funding is an opportunity to publicly discuss whether the people of Vila Marim and other stakeholders are willing to explore the possibilities of using the Tower, with the aim of preserving it physically, to maintain it as the flame of identity and pride of the inhabitants and to make it profitable, guaranteeing its sustainability and stimulating other activities, such as catering and accommodation.

Therefore, “recover and enhance to maintain and develop” will be the leitmotif.

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Las Candelas de Deleitosa. A Case Study on Heritage Education

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The present investigation is framed in the rural environment of the Villuercas, Ibores and Jara regions, an area located in the northeast of the community of Extremadura, with a wealth landscape which has an incalculable environmental value. It was declared a World Geopark by UNESCO in 2015. Its extensive natural and cultural heritage offers the opportunity to study in depth one of the great attractions of the area: the festival of Las Candelas or Purificadas, which is celebrated on February 2 in the small village of Deleitosa. This religious celebration mixes tradition, folklore, religion and culture, resulting in a true example of a popular celebration that promotes the participation of all the inhabitants of the village. Special prominence is given to the figures of the purified, the stewardess and the image of the Virgin of the Candlemas. This event not only attracts visitors from neighboring towns but also dozens of people from all over the country.

In relation to this event, we intend to carry out research work applied to heritage education and investigate the details of the festival from its base and foundation to the details of the preparations, songs, dances, clothing, rituals... Research will highlight how intergenerational dialogue acquires a special role when it comes to instilling in the youngest feelings of rootedness towards their land, their culture and their heritage, transmitting this tradition from generation to generation and conserving, valuing and feeling part of it. Finally, a workshop is proposed whose purpose is to achieve a greater diffusion of the celebration.

SESSION 2: INTERDISCIPLINARY APPROACHES

A Heritage Park in the Making: The Parrhasian Heritage Park of the Peloponnese

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The aim of this paper is to present the meticulous efforts of an international and interdisciplinary team of experts and scholars to create the first large-scale heritage park of Greece. The proposed park will extend over a mountainous 675 km² area at the junction of the Prefectures of Elis, Arcadia and Messinia, a region of major archaeological, historical and geological interest.

The initiative was launched back in 2003 with a goal to protect an area of cultural significance, outstanding natural beauty, and rich archaeological sites, while encouraging local communities to continue living and working within the protected landscape. Since then, the planning team has engaged in mapping the natural and cultural assets of the area through desk and field studies, has embarked on outreach activities, and has developed catalyst projects at the local level hoping to facilitate sustainable development and, more importantly, cultural sustainability.

Sustainable Cultural Management of the Olive Heritage for the Promotion of Culture and Local Economy: The “Routes of the Olive Tree”

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The olive tree, an emblematic tree of the Mediterranean, is part of the daily life of the Mediterranean peoples, associated with their rituals, customs and gastronomy, and has left traces of its long presence in the landscape, creating a particular culture, the “olive tree culture”.

The “Routes of the Olive Tree” promote this aspect of the modern culture of Greece and the Mediterranean, underappreciated by the general public but extremely charming and interesting. Through our activities, we aim to translate into practice an innovative approach of this significant culture and at the same time an alternative proposal for sustainable development: the organization of cultural routes and a range of related actions for their promotion.

Since their launch in 1998, the “Routes of the Olive Tree” have received numerous international distinctions. It has been officially recognised by the UNESCO as an International Cultural Route of Intercultural Dialogue & Sustainable Development in 2003 and as a Cultural Route of the Council of Europe by the Council of Europe in 2005.

These distinctions have further enabled “Routes of the Olive Tree” to forge new partnerships between olive-growing regions and to promote the olive tree culture in dozens of Mediterranean regions and in more than 10 Mediterranean countries: Greece, Turkey, Italy, Spain, France, Portugal, Lebanon, Morocco, Tunisia, Slovenia, Croatia, Spain, France, Portugal, Lebanon, Morocco, Tunisia...

The Archaeological Chart of the Municipality of Sabrosa: An Essential Tool for Managing Municipal Heritage and Territorial Planning in Rural Areas

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Archaeological and historical evidence is, essentially, an added value for the enhancement of a particular region. From our point of view, the testimonies of the past, be they structures, buildings, chapels, churches, bridges, artifacts or simply told stories, are a fundamental non-renewable resource for rural areas and communities.

Since 2017, the authors of this paper have developed a project to research, prospect, identify and record archaeological and historical remains from the past of the Municipality of Sabrosa. In essence, more than 400 sites of historical and archaeological interest were located and inventoried, covering the most varied periods in the history of human presence in the county.

Together with the prospecting and research of built testimonies, we have implemented extensive research on the county's toponymy and on some of the natural sites and landscapes referred to in historical documents, especially from the 12th century AD.

From our point of view, this is endless work, work that is constantly adapting and evolving, work that seeks to study, inventory, promote and value the cultural heritage of the municipality of Sabrosa and the Alto Douro Vinhateiro region, as well as of the Douro Demarcated Region.

In this paper we will present the most relevant aspects of the work, some of the most interesting places already identified, explore a little the archeology of the landscape and the cultural landscape in itself, and also highlight the evolution of legislation in Portugal applied to archeology and heritage preservation.

The MoCaCu Project: A Portable Unit for the Digitization, Documentation, Characterization and Conservation of Movable Cultural Heritage Artifacts in Remote Areas of Greece

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Ten years ago, rural heritage was a largely disregarded part of the cultural heritage of Greece, prey to looting, vandalism, weather conditions. In those days, the Swiss Federal Office for Culture was co-funding projects related to the protection of movable cultural heritage in “source” countries of illicit trafficking of antiquities, of which Greece was one. The University of the Peloponnese, together with Time Heritage and the IT Company Diadrasis, profited from this and designed a project based on the need for the creation of a portable unit for simultaneous interdisciplinary protection action for movable cultural heritage artifacts in remote areas of Greece. Two field works took place in the course of the project, which had a two-year-long duration: a) one in Alagonia, on the slopes of Mt. Taygetus, in villages scattered within thick vegetation and b) one in Kalarrytes, a mountainous village on the Tzoumerka range in NW Greece. In both cases the team, consisting of conservators, material analysis specialists, digitization specialists and IT specialists made sure to approach the local community. The latter overcame its initial reluctance and fear of the digitization process and offered ample information for the documentation and digital storytelling of local heritage.

The project was disseminated through posters and presentations in several conferences, as it constituted an example of how to reach out to local communities and protect rural heritage. It became inspirational not only to the people who participated and to those who attended, but also to the organizations themselves. The University of the Peloponnese established the CultTech Msc for interdisciplinary training in the relation between technology and culture, and Time Heritage got involved in a series of EU-funded and national projects aiming at rural regeneration and cultural enhancement of the countryside. At the moment, an attempt is being made to take the MoCaCu approach to a European level through the submission of the Erasmus+ KA2 proposal “Heritool”.

Historical Tungsten Mines of Vila Marim, Vila Real (Galicia-North Portugal Euroregion): An Adventure Geotourism Attraction that Supports Sustainable Conservation

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The involvement of the researchers in the Erasmus+ Project LEARNVIL (Learning Villages: Citizenship, Entrepreneurship, Heritage & Environmental Education for Rural Sustainable Development) led to this scientific paper. The project is based on the creation of ecological and social added value in villages facing demographic challenges (high aging index and depopulation). To accomplish this, the selected learning villages focus on green tractor elements: gardening, eco-agriculture, agrarian heritage, preservation of rural landscape, etc. In this way, each local community, with the support of scientists, thinks and plans its own future of sustainable development.

Vila Marim parish was nominated as a Learning Village in Portugal. The research team identified a set of historical tungsten mines in Arnal village (north of Vila Marim, Portugal) (41.337122, -7.807661). These mines are at the foot of the peak called “Cabeço”. As this mountain includes the Natural Park Alvão and as there are lodging units nearby, the idea grew to take better advantage of this forgotten heritage to create a new geotourism attraction. During the whole process, close contacts with locals were sustained; locals who also actively took part in the preparation phase, not only by pinpointing down the historical mines and temporary housing facilities for the miners, but also by cleaning up trenches. The researchers chose a mixed methodology approach: desk research, open interviews with locals, stereoscopic aerial photographs, and geological mapping.

This research allowed to map the historical mines, trenches, debris deposits, to integrate details about the tungsten-exploration in World War II (and beyond), to figure out which traditional tools have been used, and to create a geotourism itinerary. The latter allows one to read the landscape and to find out more about the local former mining activity, the importance of tungsten as a mineral for war purposes, and other tungsten explorations in North Portugal. The local population will be able to help visitors to interpret the site and its geomorphology based on the results of this micro-project.

This article mainly results from networking within the Erasmus+ Project LEARNVIL (Learning Villages: Citizenship, Entrepreneurship, Heritage & Environmental Education for Rural Sustainable Development with project number 2020-1-ES01-KA227-ADU-096064). Part of the funding was used to pay for the maps and aerial photos included in the article. David M. Freire-Lista acknowledges that his work was

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‘KALAMATA 1821, Roads of Freedom’ Project. An Interdisciplinary

Approach towards the Celebrations for the Greek War of Independence

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The "Kalamata 1821: Roads of Freedom" research project is implemented within the context of the operational program "Competitiveness, Entrepreneurship and Innovation 2014-2020 (EPAnEk)" of the Ministries of Finance and Development respectively through the joint venture of University of the Peloponnese (Coordination), the Municipally Owned Enterprise of the Municipality of Kalamata (ΦΑΠΙΣ) and the production company VIEWMASTER FILMS S.A. The research program brings together and displays the historical, cultural and social traits which contributed to the liberation of Kalamata, Greece on March 23, 1821 (Christou, 2013).

The program's three deliverables, the dramatized documentary "Wind of Freedom", based on historical events, the digital museum "Kalamata 1821", displaying the city during that era through digital maps, artistic inspirations and oral tradition and an array of cultural events happening throughout the city of Kalamata, while incorporating the elements necessary for the history of the first Greek liberated city, to be relived in commemoration of the Bicentennial of the Greek War of Independence (Panagiotidis et al, 2019). Original filmmaking, a one-of-a-kind digital museum, historical research presented through digital technologies and applications and cultural events that engage locals and visitors, are used in this program providing innovative means of dissemination and distribution of archaeological and historic information to the wider public, as well as a fundamental methodology in the sustainable development of tangible and intangible cultural heritage of modern era (Poulopoulos et al, 2019). The work portrayed presents the research and development processes of the transdisciplinary scientific team that worked together for the realization of the "Kalamata 1821: Roads of Freedom" project, in an attempt to connect the past with the present through the engagement of local stakeholders and the utilization of new technological tools in order to revive the past, preserve the memory of the local community and offer visitors an innovative and multisensory experience in their travel in time.

SESSION 3: DIGITAL APPLICATIONS

DigiSmall: Organizing Small - Local Museums Towards a Digital Era

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Over the past five years, we have observed a significant shift in various aspects of our lives, primarily in relation to technology and the digital world. This has resulted in difficulties for services and organizations with local access and influence in acquiring and maintaining their audience. One such example is small local museums, often established by individuals with a passion for folklore and tradition.

To address this, we propose a service that aims to assist these efforts in entering the digital era and enhancing their online presence. The proposed solution, the DigiSmall project, aims to connect museums, provide a common and user-friendly platform for data recording and communication, and offer a space for interaction with experts in the field. The ultimate goal is to support the social media presence and online sales of these museums.

We present the concept, the process of transforming the idea into a project, the infrastructure developed, and the current outcomes of the project.

DigiStoryteller: A Multimodal Platform and App for Local and Oral History

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The year 2023 represents in Greece the one-hundred-year anniversary of the exchange of populations with Turkey following the expulsion of these populations from Asia Minor and the Lausanne Treaty. For this occasion, a consortium consisting of the University of Western Attica, the Centre for Research on Humanities and the SMEs Diadrisis, Time Heritage and ICI-Paper have been funded by the Region of Attica to create a multimodal platform and app for displaying multimedia material and information on the refugee settlements of Attica. The project DigiStoryteller (Digital Storyteller for Refugee Attica) combines the functionalities of a database, an app guiding people along specific routes, and a crowdsourcing tool.

In selected municipalities of a refugee background, most of them urban but some semi-urban as well, selected landmarks (buildings, sites, locations) form walkable itineraries and enhance the municipality's history with texts, old photographs, songs, recipes, documents and oral testimonies by first and second generation refugees. Furthermore, a crowdsourcing modality allows inhabitants, expats and the public in general to upload their own content, thus adding a more personal overtone and increasing the feeling of shared heritage.

The DigiStoryteller modalities can be expanded to encompass many other regions, both urban and rural, both close to each other and far apart, thus showcasing oral history, local history and the regions' special historic phases in a vivid manner, contributing to local identity and sense of history, as well as to the visitors' informed guiding through their mobile phones.

Learning Villages Must Listen to Stories

Michael Meimaris

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Using examples of good practices creating community engagement through the process of the making of digital stories by citizens, we propose an “augmented” view of cultural heritage in the purpose of its revitalization. The action, as part of a larger project, consists of the following phases: School pupils visit the archeological site of Messene with their trained in digital storytelling (DST) teachers, collect data (photos, sounds, videos) and construct their polytropic relevant stories using their smartphones, working in groups (Story Circle) and individually. More precisely, during this process, participants share their story ideas, develop script, record a voice-over, select images and use video editing software to assemble all these elements into a short video. The Story Circle is at the core of the practice. This safe space offers an opportunity for the pupils- storytellers to share their story ideas and receive comments, questions and feedback from their classmates in an atmosphere of respectful listening.

The emotional experience that derives from the engagement with the discovery, selection and presentation of the appropriate each time polytropic content in the form of images, video, sound, music and narration by the story creators themselves, using the proper “language” of the digital natives for the construction of their personal empirical view of the archeological site, creates for the pupils an enriched new kind of experience, boosting at the same time skills such as creativity, empathy, strategic thinking, and different types of literacies such as information literacy, visual literacy, technological literacy, and media literacy.

The presentation of the elaborated stories as videos of limited duration (3,5 minutes max) in their schools and in the broader community could offer an added value to the entire action.

Digital Registration of Cultural Heritage Elements through a Crowdsourcing Web-Based Application

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Community participation is of great importance when it comes to local cultural heritage issues. Participation, collaboration, and co-design are practices highly suggested and appreciated by international organisations. Although desirable, involvement and deep engagement of local communities with issues related to their cultural heritage is not always achievable.

To address this, we implemented a design thinking project with the community of a rural area in central Greece that lacks motivation to participate in collaborative cultural activities. Design thinking, as a problem-solving methodology offers tools to uncover problems and provides opportunities for innovative and effective solutions.

This paper presents the workload followed during the design thinking process as well as PolLog, the digital product that was designed and developed as an outcome of the process. PolLog is a crowdsourcing web-based application that uses a geolocation service and a very simple interface to facilitate mapping of tangible and intangible cultural heritage elements that we call Points of Interest.

Pannonias Medieval Digital Old Lands: Digital Humanities, History and Archaeology for Culture and Tourism

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The ancient “high-medieval lands of Pannonias” essentially comprise three municipalities: the municipality of Vila Real, the municipality of Sabrosa and the municipality of Alijo, in Trás-os-Montes and Alto Douro, north of the Douro River, between Régua and the municipalities to the east. During the period of the Suevi Kingdoms, from around the 5th to the 8th centuries, this territory was organised administratively into parishes, as evidenced by the document Parochiale Sueuorum (Suevian Parish) or Divisio Theodemiri, a document issued by the Council of Braga in the second half of the 6th century.

The “Pannonias Medieval Digital Old Lands” project is a historical, archaeological and heritage enhancement project focusing on these ancient territories. The aim is to integrate various monuments, about 30 monuments, in a digital platform, with a virtual guide, “The Druid”, who will make the guided tours to the sites digitally and in person to the communities of young people and tourists. An interpretative centre will also be implemented with an immersive room, virtual reality and an exhibition room on the “Ancient Lands of Pannonias”.

All monuments are scanned, using LIDAR technology, by drone and also by terrestrial photogrammetry. The Guide, “The Druid”, is also digitalised, implementing an animation through Open Source software and an application with the possibility of virtual reality is also implemented for each monument, integrating the set of monuments in several trails.

This is a project for cultural and touristic valorisation and dissemination which, using the various digital Humanities technologies, promotes the territory, its people, its traditions and its monuments in an innovative and dynamic way. The project's partners are Sabrosa Town Council, Alijo Town Council, Murça Town Council, and the Regional Directorate for Culture of the North and Tourism of Porto and the North.

SESSION 4: SUSTAINABILITY AND BIODIVERSITY

Nutritional Self-Sufficiency in Krini Trikalon and the Active Role of the Cultural Association of Krini

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A new order of things looms on the horizon of the rural landscape of the Thessalian plain. The production of local products (meat, dairy, honey, nuts, wine, grains, and fruit and vegetables) seems to be gaining ground both in terms of production adequacy and availability. The modern way of farming promotes an abundance of quality and marketable goods to the available market, providing the possibility of flexibility in terms of their availability in the domestic market.

The producers not only have self-sufficiency in the goods produced in the richly cultivated rural landscapes of the municipal district of Krini, but also proceed to make them available to buyers in the Region of Thessaly. Domestic production exceeds domestic demand. In fact, in the last decade practices of exchanging local products between producers have been observed, always based on the monetary value of each product.

The role that the Cultural Association of Krini comes to play is, on the one hand, to record in a scientific way the products, the quantity of production per hectare, as well as the cultivation methods applied. It also aims to raise the awareness of growers regarding issues of safeguarding biodiversity, through informative activities.

The first action of last year concerned the organization of a conference on the importance of the bee to humans and to the biodiversity of the region. The association's second action, which took place successfully last summer, was aimed at the collection and preservation of traditional seeds as well as nutritional self-sufficiency. The role and ultimate purpose of the association is to raise awareness of the protection of the environment, the cultivation of local products, and the quality assurance of the cultivation and the products, with a view to self-sufficiency, thus ensuring the preservation of the cultural tradition of our region.

Jupiter

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Precision farming has the potential to revolutionize the way farming is done, but high costs associated with smart farming technologies have made it challenging for small farmers to adopt them. Jupiter's system, consisting of a modular monitoring device and a master device, allows for the collection of various parameters such as soil and air temperature, humidity, electric conductivity, pH, nitrogen, sodium, potassium, and more. The system is powered by a battery and solar panel and communicates with the master device through LoRa WAN connectivity. Jupiter's affordability and versatility make it ideal for small farmers, enabling them to optimize resource use, improve product quality, and reduce CO2 emissions. With 97% of agricultural land in Europe managed by small-scale farmers, the Jupiter system represents a significant step forward in leveling the playing field and enabling small farmers to compete with larger agribusinesses. The mission of Jupiter is to bring precision farming technology to small-scale farmers.

Learning Villages with Value: The Case of the LEARNVIL Approach in Vila Marim, Portugal

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Villages are places of memory space whose perpetuation over time will surely infer new activation dynamics. In recent years, many programs, projects and actors who have discussed experiences of combating desertification of villages and strategies for their economic revitalization. The increasing valuation of villages in recent years seems to be oriented towards consumption, partly due to the loss of relevance of agriculture, and partly due to the centrality that other economic activities associated with tourism and leisure have acquired.

This communication presents the actions developed in the framework of the Erasmus+ Project LEARNVIL (*Learning Villages: Citizenship, Entrepreneurship, Heritage & Environmental Education for Rural Sustainable Development*) in Vila Marim, a parish in the northern interior of Portugal, between the years 2021 and 2023. The results show that socioeconomic, learning, self-esteem and rural experience dynamics were mobilized, which are likely to be associated with feelings of quality of life, economic revitalization scenarios, and the commercialization of new and old products.

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Terra Maronesa, a Collaborative Community that Invests in Networking

Carla C. Cunha de Sousa, Veronika Joukes

This communication explores the potential of the collaborative community “Terra Maronesa” as an engine for starting partnerships and an active member of various collaborative networks.

The Terra Maronesa Association - Practical Community for Sustainable Development - values the autochthonous Maronesa cow breed in its different aspects: cultural, social/economic, environmental and tourism. At the centre of its attention are agricultural, livestock and pastoral activities which promote local development in this rural area threatened with depopulation, ensuring better preservation and enhancement of resources and heritage, as well as a fair return for people working locally.

Terra Maronesa has already created a Shepherd School, the Life Maronesa project and the Terra Maronesa Academy; it is part of the Colab InnovGastronomy and collaborates with the Erasmus+ LEARNVIL project.

The parish of Vila Marim, involved in the Learning Villages project, is part of the Serra do Alvão (municipalities of Vila Real, Ribeira de Pena, Vila Pouca de Aguiar and Mondim de Basto). This region is covered by the Terra Maronesa project.

The similarity of integrated strategies for sustainable valorisation between the LEARNVIL and Terra Maronesa projects, through a common approach, naturally allowed the establishment of collaborative actions between these projects. This sharing of knowledge and skills has allowed supporting the co-creation of integrated dynamics of recovery and sustainable valorisation of the territories covered, through a community-based, systemic and transdisciplinary approach, oriented towards the creation of economic, cultural and social value.

Dialogue and Action for the Future: Developing the Community-Led Revitalisation of a Small Mountain Village through a Multi-Stakeholder Model

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Small villages face the challenge of growth and development in a changing world and are constantly declining in terms of demographics, local economic and social structures. However, even smaller communities can become agents of change: this project is about raising awareness, building the necessary capacities as well as infrastructure not only to avoid demographic shrinkage but also to revitalise the community in a more viable and sustainable way.

The Civic Europe incubator through the Idea Challenge grants aims to support ideas & projects in places characterised by a lack or dysfunction of community spaces and little or no civil society infrastructure. These are places in Central, Eastern and Southern Europe where people do not understand that they can be active members of their communities, and lack the necessary skills to participate in social and civic life.

Rural Areas: Smart Tips on the Road to the Sustainability

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It is well-known that the rural areas have to make a real long and intense effort in order for them to survive or grow in the contemporary competitive environment. On this difficult road to sustainability, and beyond the general and sectoral policies, measures and actions, the villages can use some smart tips in order to enhance or facilitate their efforts.

Tip 1: Local democracy initiatives: in the small communities it is potentially easier to gather a considerable proportion of the citizens for bottom-up procedures.

Tip 2: Research, pilot projects: for the same reason, because of their small size, rural communities could be ideal test-beds for innovative actions.

Tip 3: Extroversion: rural communities have to take part in European programmes and initiatives on equal terms with the big cities in order for them to open their perspectives and stay competitive.

Tip 4: Leveraging pros: both cultural heritage and natural landscape are usually the most important assets of the rural areas. Digitisation makes the task to “gather” and combine them easier than ever.

Farkadona tried to follow these tips, with more or less success. Youth Council, Local Action Group, Poi-Log, European Projects and Initiatives, are some of these efforts. Our experience indicates that the first step is to have a specific plan that includes all the necessary sources (know-how, human resources, financing). After this, all these tips can be incorporated in the main municipal policies of the midterm programming period and provide a boost for them.

PARTICIPANTS

Konstantinos Asikis is a PhD-candidate and researcher on Urban Planning & Regional Development at the Architecture School of the National Technical University of Athens. He graduated as a Civil Engineer-Transport from the School of Mechanical Engineering at the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki and holds a MSc in Spatial Planning (Clermont-Ferrand University). His accreditations and affiliations include the following: EIT-PROSPECT Professional Certification on Innovative Financing for Climate Actions, UTH-DEVOPS Certificated Smart Cities Planner, National Certificates on Local Development, EPLO Certificate on European Funds. Hellenic Healthy Cities Network (WHO) Scientific Board, WHO-HCN-UN Habitat Working Groups, POLIS–Eurocities-DG Move Safe City Streets Initiative, EIT-Mobility Experts Database. He is Head of the Strategic/Operational Planning & ICT Department at the Municipality of Farkadona, as well as Project Manager and EU Projects Partner Coordinator.

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Mark Davison is the Park Planning Manager at the City of Boulder. Prior to this, Mark led planning, design, and environmental education efforts for Oregon State Parks and the National Park Service. His career has focused on park planning, park design, visitor experience, natural land management and environmental conservation. He has worked on numerous projects in Europe and the United States as well as teaching at the University of Oregon, the Parthassian Heritage Park Field School and is Co-Principal Investigator for Park Planning at the Parthassian Heritage Park, an effort to develop the first National Park in Greece. He received his Masters in Landscape Architecture at the University of Pennsylvania and attended Manchester University in England for his undergraduate degree in Landscape Design.

David Martín Freire-Lista is a Spanish early career researcher. He holds a European PhD in Geology and Geological Engineering (2016) and a Master in Environmental Geology and Geological Resources from the Complutense University of Madrid (2010). His research is mainly focused on petrophysics for heritage stones conservation, on the controls of stone decay, both in natural environments and in the context of natural and stone-built heritage. He has special interest in Non-Destructive Techniques for protection, conservation and restoration of cultural heritage. He is currently employed with a postdoc fellowship as full researcher at the Centre of Geosciences (CGeo-UTAD) of Portugal. In this capacity he is responsible for a heritage stones project. He has worked at College of London University at Qatar (2018); at the “Applied Petrology for Heritage Conservation” of Geosciences Institute (from 2008 to 2018) in Madrid, Spain. He has also worked at the Department of Biology, Ecology and Earth Sciences at the University of Calabria (Italy, 2015), at the Bureau of Economic Geology (University of Texas at Austin, USA, 2004-2005), at the Simón Bolívar University (Venezuela, 2002-2004), at the Federal University of Ouro Preto (Brasil, 2001-2002), at the Federal University of Minas Gerais (Brasil, 2000-2001), and Oviedo University (Spain, 2000). He particularly enjoys collaborating with scientists from different disciplines to develop new skills and solve new challenges. He has published 28 scientific articles in high-impact indexed journals, and he is a regular reviewer of more than 10 high-impact indexed journals. His Open Researcher and Contributor ID can be seen in <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-6411-4002>.

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Gerardo Vidal Gonçalves graduated in History. He holds a master’s degree in archeology and environment and is a guest researcher at CIDEHUS at the University of Évora. He also holds a postgraduate degree in Archeology and Prehistory. He carried out a research internship in dendrochronology at CONICET / IANIGLA, in Mendoz, Argentina and took part in the European Project MEDINS (Mediterranean Intangible Space) on intangible cultural heritage. He collaborates with the TPTI Masters at the University of Évora (History Department) and specializes in Digital Humanities (multidimensional digitization of built cultural heritage and cultural and scientific digital modeling and communication). He is currently, through AHAS, the coordinator of the LVIN-C project, supporting research, management and communication

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George Karabatos has a long experience in the tourism sector and specialist in tourism marketing. He was for 20 years General Manager of the Hotel, Conference & Sports Complex ELITE VILLAGE in Kalamata, whose management and high level of service was awarded the 1st Prize by the International Award for Hotel and Catering Industry. He has been President of the Arab-Greek Chamber and for three consecutive 4-year terms he was President of the Messinia Chamber of Commerce and Industry with extensive activity at Euro-Mediterranean level. Initiator of the internationally recognized cultural Route of the Olive Tree, he is currently Executive Director of the Foundation of the same name and from January 2023 President of the Euro-Mediterranean Network of Mediterranean Olive Oil Towns (RECOMED Network).

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Theodoros Lakiaras was born in 1974 in the village of Krini near Trikala in Thessaly. He is a municipal employee, a student of Medicine of the University of Athens, a photojournalist as well as the owner of the electronic newspaper of the Municipality of Farkadona <https://krinilive.gr>. He is the founder and the vice president of the Cultural Association of Krini, and was the organizer and chairman of the organizing committee of the 1st Conference on the History and Culture of Farkadona held in Farkadona in December 2015. He has participated in workshops and conferences on topics related to tradition and culture, environment and rural development. He has a long-standing contribution to local events in the area of the Municipality of Farkadona as a volunteer in actions and initiatives by local associations and unions.

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Tiberio Moscardelli holds a BA in mechanical engineering. He is a STEM specialist and product designer. He is in charge of the development of the project Jupiter and coordinates the STEM projects. He has expertise in inclusion practices and in quality management supervision in production.

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Maria Pritsiouli was born, grew up and lives for long periods in the village of Krini near Trikala, in the municipality of Farkadona. She works as a teacher in secondary education. She is involved in arts and letters, special education, intercultural education and technology in education. She graduated from the Department of Philology of the University of Patras (2006) with a postgraduate education in Special Education (2013), and holds a Master's degree in Management of Cultural Information (Ionian University, 2020). She has attended conferences, workshops and events on education, culture and agricultural issues related to her place of origin. Together with her husband, she runs a modern 23-acre nut farm in the area of Krini, according to standards that promise excellent quality domestic products and respecting the environmental footprint. She contributes to the Cultural Association of Krini in her capacity as a philologist. She is the mother of Euthymia and Vassilis.

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David Gilman Romano, Ph.D., is Nicholas and Athena Karabots Professor of Greek Archaeology in the School of Anthropology at the University of Arizona and he directs the Archaeological Mapping Lab at the University of Arizona. His interests include Greek and Roman cities and sanctuaries, Greek and Roman athletics including the ancient Olympic Games, Roman centuriation and land planning and computer applications in archaeology. Dr. Romano has been a pioneer in computerized mapping, digital cartography, remote sensing and GIS in the study of ancient Greek and Romano cities and sanctuaries. Since 2004 he has been Co- Director and Field Director of the Mt. Lykaion Excavation and Survey Project in Arcadia, Greece, and the Director of the Initiative for the creation of the Parrhasian Heritage Park of the Peloponnesos, Greece’s first large scale national heritage park. His publications include Athletics and Mathematics in Archaic Corinth: The Origins of the Greek Stadion (1993), The Catalogue of the Classical Collection of the Glencairn Museum, Bryn Athyn (1998) with Irene Bald Romano, Mapping Augustan Rome (2002) in collaboration with Lothar Haselberger, as well as a series of publications on the city and landscape planning of the Roman colony of Corinth and, with Mary Voyatzis, on the results of the excavations at the Sanctuary of Zeus at Mt. Lykaion. Dr. Romano is the Co-Editor of the projected four-volume series on the results of the excavations at the Sanctuary of Zeus at Mt. Lykaion to be published through the American School of Classical Studies at Athens.

Francisco Javier Barra Sanz was born in Cáceres (Spain) in 1980. He studied compulsory education in a public school, and then did other studies that he never finished. At the age of 18 he started to work for the Catholic Church, and it was there that he came into contact with the world of art, historical heritage and music. At the age of 32 he decided to take a big academic step and took the exams to enter the University of Extremadura. He decided to choose the degree in Primary Education, which he completed with a special mention in music education. Afterwards, he took the Master's Degree in Social Anthropology, specialising in Cultural Heritage. Nowadays he is doing a PhD on the management, cataloguing and conservation of musical heritage. He is the titular organist of the Church of San Juan Bautista in Caceres City and works as a researcher at the University of Extremadura.

Teresa Sequeira holds a degree in Economics (University of Porto). In 2006 she completed a PhD also in Economics (University of Trás-os-Montes and Alto Douro - UTAD). Her professional career began in 1987 at the SONA E group, where she was a senior manager, namely at the sub-holding SONA E Real Estate and Tourism. She was also a member of the Board of SPIDOURO, SA, where she promoted several structuring projects of Regional Development and private projects in the field of tourism. T. Sequeira has been a professor at UTAD since 1992, having published several scientific papers. Her research area is focused on the issues of Regional and Sustainable Development, Investment, European Union and Social Cohesion. Currently, she is structuring the project “National Road 2 Observatory”, involving a network of higher education institutions, municipalities and private agents.

Carla C. Cunha de Sousa is a Portuguese Landscape Architect with experience in projects in the areas of environment, cultural heritage and rural development. She has a Master’s degree in Landscape Architecture (2015), a postgraduate degree in Tourism - Local Resources, Animation and Development (2008) and a degree in Landscape Architecture (2003) from the University of Trás-os-Montes e Alto Douro (UTAD). She has training in “Anthropology Methodologies for Intangible Cultural Heritage” by the Research Network Centre in Anthropology (CRIA), accredited by UNESCO under the Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Heritage. She promotes valorisation initiatives in rural territories within the scope of the project “Terra Maronesa”, and is part of the community that safeguards the Alvão mountain range in its different economic, cultural, social, environmental and touristic aspects. She participated in the program “Douro Criativo” - UTAD, oriented to the development of projects and research focusing on landscape, heritage and environment, with the project “Hortus with History”. She was part of the implementation team of the project HIGRO - Demonstrative Actions for the Conservation of Priority Mountain Habitats in Northern Portugal in the Alvão and Marão Mountains. She worked for the project “Archaeological Heritage - Roman Mines of Tresminas”, in collaboration with the archaeologists Jurgen Wahl and Regula Wahl-Clerciri. She co-organised the 10th Summer Workshop on Landscape Architecture at UTAD with the title “The Roman Gold Landscape, a journey through time and space in Tresminas”. She has worked at the Municipality of Vila Pouca de Aguiar, participating in the elaboration of detailed plans for the recovery of historical areas. Her areas of interest are sustainable rural development, environmental education, citizenship and heritage valuation.

Yorgos Tzedopoulos studied in Athens and Vienna. He holds a PhD in Modern Greek History from the University of Athens. His publications and research interests deal with issues of

social and cultural history between the 16th and the 20th century, as well as with public history and historical memory in the digital age. He has taught at postgraduate programmes of the Ionian University and the University of the Peloponnese on the interaction of history and digital technology, and is a teaching fellow at the Department of History and Archaeology at the University of Ioannina (Early Modern Greek history). He is a member of the “Greek Infrastructure Network for the Humanities” that is supported by the Academy of Athens within the framework of the DARIAH network. Since 2014 he participates in projects and European programmes on history, cultural heritage and management as a member of the Time Heritage team.

Martín Gómez-Ullate has a PhD in Social Anthropology. Senior researcher, professor and project manager with more than ten years’ experience in conducting and participating in international, cross-border, national and local R+D projects based on cultural management, applied anthropology, cooperation and local development. He has been selected in the Program of Attraction and Retention of Research Talent for the Region of Extremadura to develop research in the field of Immaterial Cultural Heritage Management for Sustainable Tourism in the University of Extremadura (Teacher Training College). He has coordinated the European Project, CULTOUR+, CULTURAL+, LEARNVIL (Erasmus+ Strategic Partnerships for Higher and Adult Education). He has directed the Scientific Committee in the International Conference "Cultural Management and Governance for European Pilgrimage Routes and Religious Tourism". He has published several research works about pilgrims and pilgrimage, musical heritage, cultural routes, and cultural tourism. His research webpage is: <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Martin-Gomez-Ullate>.

Vasiliki Valantou is a graduate of the Department of History, Archaeology and Cultural Resources Management of the University of the Peloponnese” with a MSc in Cultural Heritage Materials and Technologies and a specialization in Thin Section petrography at the University College London. During her collaboration with the Department and the Laboratory of Archaeometry, she has been a member of the Programme “Mobile Care for the Documentation, Characterisation and Conservation of Movable Cultural Heritage Artefacts from Remote Areas in Greece (MoCaCu)” 2013-2015; a member of the Organizing Committee of the 41st International Archaeometry Symposium held in Kalamata Greece in May 2016 as well as of the 3rd, 4th and 5th ARCH_RNT Symposia organized by the Laboratory of Archaeometry; served as Administrative Officer for the MSc in Cultural Heritage Materials and Technologies (CultTech) and for the MA in Administration and Promotion of Cultural Resources and the Environment”. Currently is a member of the EU

funded Programme KALAMATA 1821: Roads of Freedom. Her research focuses mainly on pottery and mortars through mineralogical analysis, using a polarized microscope and a Scanning Electron Microscope coupled with an Energy Dispersive Spectrometer (SEM/EDS), investigating issues of chemical composition and manufacturing technology. In latest years Cultural Heritage has been also a main field of interest as she is a licensed tourist guide, has attended seminars in Museum Education and has collaborated in digital applications for Cultural Heritage projects. Currently she is a PhD candidate at the University of Peloponnese focusing mainly on pottery and mortars through mineralogical analysis, investigating issues of chemical composition and manufacturing technology. In the field of Cultural Heritage, is a licensed tourist guide, has attended seminars in Museum Education and collaborated in digital applications for Cultural Heritage projects.

Mary Voyatzis is trained as a Classical Archaeologist and has been working in Greece for over 35 years. Her research areas involve Ancient Greek ritual and religion, sanctuaries and their development over time, and ancient Greek pottery. Dr. Voyatzis was a Principal Investigator in the excavations at the sanctuary of Athena Alea at Tegea, 1990-1994, and she is currently a co-director of the Mt. Lykaion Excavation and Survey project (since 2004).

Dr. Manolis Wallace [<http://gav.uop.gr/wallace/>], Associate Professor at the Department of Informatics and Telecommunications and Director of the Knowledge and Uncertainty Research Laboratory (ΓΑΒ LAB) [<http://gav.uop.gr/>], has a long experience in the management of educational and research organizations from his previous tenures at the University of Indianapolis and at the Foundation of the Hellenic World. He now transfers this experience to Tripolis and the University of Peloponnese. In his tenure at the Foundation of the Hellenic World he supervised the implementation of CH related projects of a cumulative budget exceeding 10Meuros. Currently, at the University of the Peloponnese, he leads an interdisciplinary team including researchers from IT, researchers from the humanities as well as the local Ephorate of Antiquities, jointly working towards using technology for the understanding of cultural heritage and its presentation to the broader public.

Prof. Nikolaos Zacharias studied Chemical Engineering at the National Technical University of Athens (Metsovion) and carried out his MSc and PhD at the NCSR Demokritos in the field of luminescence dating supported by a scholarship from the Ministry of Research and Development. He then realized 2 post-doctoral programmes at Bonn University (GEOPRO/FP5) and at Demokritos (IKY/State Scholarships Foundation). From 2004 – 2009 he worked as researcher at Demokritos and as visiting staff member at the Technological

Educational Institute of Piraeus. Since 2009 he has joined the University of the Peloponnese (Chair of the Dept. of History, Archaeology and Cultural Resources Management, November 2015-). He is member of the Board of the Hellenic Society for Archaeometry, and Member of the International Symposium on Archaeometry Standing Committee. He has published extensively (over 140 peer-reviewed papers, book chapters and symposia proceedings) in the fields of luminescence dating, pottery and glass analysis, characterization and provenance.